

TABLE 2—SELECTED INFRARED FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF DNR AND COMPLEXES

Compd.	$\nu_{O...H...O}$	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{N=O}$
DNR*		1690	1660, 1640 s $\nu_{C=N}$
(Li-gly) ₂ .DNR	2700 br	1620	1590
(Na-β-alanine) ₂ .DNR	2700 br	1660, 1625	1580
(K-8HQ) ₂ .DNR	2650 br	1650, 1620	1590
(K-Anth) ₂ .DNR	2650 br	1660 s, 1620	1590
(K-ONBA) ₂ .DNR		1650, 1620	1575
[(Mg(8HQ) ₂)] ₂ .DNR	2740	1630, 1610	1520
[Mg(SalH) ₂] ₂ .DNR		1630	1520
[Ca(SalH) ₂] ₂ .DNR	2740 br	1600 s	
[Mg(ONP) ₂] ₂ .DNR	2720 br	1600 s	1560
[Ca(ONP) ₂] ₂ .DNR	2720 br	1610	1550
[Mg(Anth) ₂] ₂ .DNR	2720 br	1620	1560

* ν_{O-H} 3540, 3420.

down with reduced intensity, and a new band of medium intensity at ~ 2700 cm⁻¹ is seen in the complexes, which suggest the presence of strong hydrogen bonding. The 1690 cm⁻¹ peak of DNR shifts down to 1660-1600 cm⁻¹ in complexes, which indicate coordination through C=O. The 1660 cm⁻¹ peak with a shoulder at 1640 cm⁻¹ in DNR which is probably due to N=O, is absent in complexes. Instead, one peak is obtained at 1590-1520 cm⁻¹; this may be the C=N peak, which might have coordinated to the metal.

Thermodynamics of Non-Electrolyte Solutions. I. Excess Volumes of Binary Mixtures of 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane with some Alcohols at 40°

O. P. YADAV, S. P. KHATKAR and R. C. SAINI

Chemistry and Biochemistry Department,
Haryana Agricultural University, Hissar-125 004

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EARLIER¹⁻⁵, excess thermodynamic functions for binary systems containing n-alkane as one of the components have been reported. Benson *et al.*¹ reported excess volumes of C₅- to C₁₆-n-alkanes in n-decanol. Jain *et al.*^{2,3,10} studied excess functions for some n-alkanes in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and silicon tetrachloride. Excess enthalpies of some n-alkanes in cyclohexane have also been reported by some workers⁴⁻⁶. However, the thermodynamic data for isomeric alkanes is only limited^{7,8}. In order to see the effect of branching of alkanes on the magnitude of excess

thermodynamic functions, we have undertaken a systematic study of thermodynamics of isomeric alkanes solutions consisting of solvents of different molecular shape and size. We report here excess volumes of five binary systems of iso-octane (2,2,4-trimethylpentane) with some normal or branched aliphatic alcohols.

Experimental

Chemicals: 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane (L. R. grade) was distilled over sodium metal. Ethanol was purified by distilling a mixture of absolute alcohol and benzene (10:1) where fractions distilling at 64.8° (a ternary azeotrope of benzene, alcohol and water) and at 68.2° (a binary azeotrope of alcohol and benzene) were rejected. Pure alcohol left behind was further distilled over sodium metal.

n-Butanol (L.R. grade), isopropanol (A.R. grade), iso-butanol (for synthesis) and isoamyl alcohol (L.R. grade) were simply distilled before use.

Purity of chemicals was checked by comparing their density and boiling points with the corresponding available literature values⁹.

Method: A bicapillary pycnometer (about 10 ml capacity) was used for measuring the densities of pure components and their mixture at 40°. The details of the apparatus and the method are described elsewhere¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

From the densities of pure components and their mixtures, molar excess volumes have been calculated using the equation

$$v^E = (M_1x_1 + M_2x_2)/d - M_1x_1/d_1 - M_2x_2/d_2 \quad (1)$$

where, v^E is the molar excess volume in ml mol⁻¹, M_i , x_i , and d_i are the molecular weight, the mole fraction and the density of the component i ($i=1, 2$), respectively; d is the density of the mixture.

In Table 1, molar excess volumes of the studied binary systems have been presented. Plots of v^E vs mole fractions of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane have been depicted in Fig. 1. The magnitude of excess volumes at equimolar concentration for the studied alcoholic systems is in the order: isopropanol > ethanol > isobutanol > n-butanol > isoamyl alcohol. It is evident that maximum value of excess volume for each system lies over a composition rich in 2,2,4-trimethylpentane (Fig. 1).

TABLE 1—MOLAR EXCESS VOLUMES (v^E) FOR BINARY SYSTEMS OF 2,2,4-TRIMETHYLPENTANE WITH SOME ALIPHATIC ALCOHOLS AT 40°

x_1 *	Ethanol	n-Butanol	Isopropanol	Isobutanol	Isoamyl alcohol
0.1	0.17	-0.02	0.23	0.01	-0.08
0.2	0.32	0.01	0.43	0.08	-0.03
0.3	0.44	0.09	0.61	0.16	0.07
0.4	0.54	0.17	0.73	0.24	0.16
0.5	0.59	0.24	0.80	0.33	0.23
0.6	0.63	0.33	0.82	0.42	0.30
0.7	0.61	0.40	0.79	0.55	0.34
0.8	0.55	0.43	0.71	0.44	0.36
0.9	0.43	0.40	0.57	0.40	0.32

* x_1 = Mole fraction of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane.

It is observed (Fig. 1) that the magnitude of v^E decreases with the increase of chain length of alkanols. Earlier, a similar dependence of excess volumes on the chain length of alkanols in carbon tetrachloride was observed¹¹ by Ramavarma and Kumaran. However, Benson *et al.*¹ while studying excess volumes of binary mixtures of n-alkanes (C_8 to C_{16}) in n-decanol, observed that excess volumes increase with the increase of chain length of n-alkane component.

Fig. 1. Plot of v^E vs x_1 for some alcohols in 2,2,4-trimethylpentane: \square —Isopropanol, \bullet —ethanol, \circ —isobutanol, \times —butanol, Δ —isoamyl alcohol.

For the systems containing ethanol or isopropanol, the excess volumes are positive over the entire mole fraction range. However, for the remaining three systems (*viz.* 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + n-butanol; + isobutanol; + isoamyl alcohol), v^E vs mole fraction curves are sigmoid with negative values over the region rich in alcohol component and the positive values in the region rich

in 2,2,4-trimethylpentane. The positive volume change may be explained in terms of the predominant intermolecular hydrogen bond stretching of associated alcohol molecules in the presence of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane. The negative values of excess volumes may be due to the predominant structural effects which arise from interstitial accommodation and changes of free volumes. The observed decrease of excess volumes with the increase of chain length of the alkanol component in the studied systems is an obvious outcome of the fact that the capability for the interstitial accommodation of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane molecules within the branched structure of the alkanol multimers increases with the increasing length of alcohol molecule.

The higher values of excess volumes in case of the solutions containing isobutanol in comparison to n-butanol solutions is due to more hindered interstitial adjustments of unlike molecules owing to the steric effect in case of the former solutions.

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Kinetics of Copper(II)-catalysed Oxidation of Formic Acid by Peroxodisulphate Ion

S. C. GOYAL* and L. K. SAXENA

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra-282 002

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EXTENSIVE studies on peroxodisulphate oxidation reactions in catalysed and uncatalysed conditions have been reported^{1,2}. A few investigations dealt with the catalytic effect of

*Chemical Laboratory, J. K. Tyrecord Ltd., Kota.